

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the seventh regular issue in 2017. First, allow me to gratefully thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. Second, I'd like to encourage researchers to apply for a membership in our editorial board - if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please send me your curriculum vitae and a publication list to cguetl@iicm.edu. We'd also like to extend the J.UCS consortium by further partners from the North American and Asia-Pacific region; please contact me if you and your organization are interested in joining and supporting J.UCS. Finally, we are also interested in high quality proposals of special issues covering emerging topics and new trends so if you consider editing a special issue, please contact me at cguetl@iicm.edu.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 3 accepted papers from 3 different countries and two continents.

Enrique Chavarriaga, Francisco Jurado and Fernando Díez from Spain introduce in their research about an interpreter able to evaluate programs coded in high-level XML-based domain specific languages providing solutions to domain specific problems within a web-client application. Alexandros Fakis, Georgios Karopoulos and Georgios Kambourakis from Greece present and analyze their approach for preserving privacy in SIP signaling by using an onion-routing approach where selected sensitive fields of SIP messages are encrypted using either asymmetric or symmetric encryption. Finally, in a collaborative research between Argentinian and Spanish research institutions, Cecilia Sanz, Verónica Artola, Andrea Guisen, Javier Marco, Eva Cerezo and Sandra Baldassarri introduce and present findings about ACoTI, an assessment process on a tangible interaction application oriented to individuals with complex communication needs.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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